

Chemical Constituents of *Rhamnus procumbens*. Application of ^{13}C NMR Spectroscopy in Structure Elucidation

P. L. MAJUMDER* and ANASUA CHATTOPADHYAY (Neé BAGCHI)

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, University of Calcutta, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 30 April 1984, accepted 30 August 1985

Musizin (1a), physcion (2a), emodin (2c), chrysophanol (2e), frangulin A (2f), kaemferide (3) and 7-hydroxy-5-methoxyphthalide (4) were isolated from *Rhamnus procumbens*. Some of the spectral data of these compounds not reported earlier were studied for the first time. Detailed ^{13}C nmr spectral analyses of musizin (1a), musizin diacetate (1b), physcion diacetate (2b), emodin triacetate (2d), pentaacetyl derivative of frangulin A (2g) and kaemferide (3) were made, and the diagnostic spectral features of these compounds are discussed.

PLANTS of the genus *Rhamnus* (Fam. : Rhamnaceae) are well known for their varied medicinal properties^{1,2}. Extracts of some of these plants are used as purgatives^{1,2}. This has interested us to chemically investigate the *Rhamnus* species, *Rhamnus procumbens*, on which there is no previous report of any chemical study. Solvent extraction of the whole plant of *R. procumbens* and usual chromatography of the extracts have resulted in the isolation of seven compounds which have been identified with musizin³ (1a), physcion⁴ (2a), emodin^{1,5} (2c), chrysophanol¹ (2e), frangulin A^{1,6} (2f), kaemferide⁷ (3) and 7-hydroxy-5-methoxy-phthalide⁸ (4). In case of emodin and physcion the identity was established by direct comparison with the respective authentic samples. The remaining compounds were characterised by their various spectral data due to non-availability of authentic samples. For all the compounds, some of the spectral data which were not recorded earlier were studied for the first time. This paper, while describing the isolation and characterisation of the above compounds, deals with detailed ^{13}C nmr spectral analyses of some of the major compounds and their more soluble derivatives, viz. musizin (1a), musizin diacetate (1b), physcion diacetate (2b), emodin triacetate (2d), pentaacetyl frangulin A (2g) and kaemferide (3). The carbon chemical shifts of these compounds are recorded in Table 1. The degree of protonation of the carbon atoms in each compound was determined by off-resonance decoupling and the assignments of the carbon resonances were made by comparison with the δ_{C} values of structurally related compounds and using the known additive parameters of the functional groups.

The carbon resonances of musizin not only support the presence of two phenolic hydroxyl groups, an acetyl and a methyl function in a naphthalene skeleton, but also confirm their relative positions. Although the additive parameters for the various functional groups in benzene^{9,10} parallel

those in naphthalene, the values show considerable differences. A new set of additive parameters for OH at C-1, COCH_3 and CH_3 at C-2 of naphthalene have been derived by comparison of the reported δ_{C} values^{10,11} of α -naphthol, β -naphthyl methyl ketone and β -methylnaphthalene with those of parent naphthalene. Using these additive parameters, the calculated carbon chemical shifts for the structure 1a for musizin were found to be in excellent agreement with the observed values except for C-1, C-2 and C-8, which showed downfield shifts of 8.92, 5.69 and 5.32 ppm, respectively. The downfield shift of C-1 and C-2 may be attributed partly to the additional effect of the substituents OH, COCH_3 and CH_3 being placed on consecutive carbon atoms. This finds analogy with similar downfield shifts of substituted carbon atoms of 1,2,3-trioxygenated benzene derivatives^{12,13}. Intramolecular hydrogen bonding between OH at C-1 and COCH_3 at C-2 may also be partly responsible for such downfield shifts of C-1 and C-2. The observed deshielding of C-8 of musizin may be due to the *peri* interaction of the hydroxyl groups at C-1 and C-8. This effect, in turn, may also partly contribute to the deshielding of C-1. The effect of such *peri* interaction has also been observed⁹ in the downfield shift of C-1 and C-8 of 1,8-dimethylnaphthalene by ~ 1.8 ppm. The assignments of the carbon chemical shifts of musizin (1a) was further supported by the ^{13}C nmr spectral data of its diacetyl derivative (1b). Except the additional signals for the two acetyl groups, the carbon resonances of 1b are essentially similar to those of 1a, the differences being those expected for a changed additive parameters due to the replacement of the two hydroxyl groups of 1a by two acetoxy functions in 1b. The ^{13}C nmr spectral data of musizin and its diacetate thus not only confirm their assigned structures, but also provide useful information for future ^{13}C nmr spectral recognition of new members of this series. It may be mentioned in this connection that the isolation of musizin from *R.*

TABLE 1—CARBON CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF 1a, 1b, 2b, 2d, 2g and 3

Carbon atoms	Chemical shifts in δ (multiplicity)					
	1a ^a	1b ^b	2b ^b	2d ^b	2g ^b	3 ^a
C-1	155.2 (s)	140.9 (s)	151.9 (s)	151.2 (s)	152.1 (s)	—
C-2	124.3 (s)	131.5 (s)	115.9 (d)	123.2 (d)	117.7 (d)	148.6 (s)
C-3	134.4 (s)	134.2 (s)	163.5 (s)	154.5 (s)	159.5 (s)	137.9 (s)
C-4	120.0 (d)	125.9 (d)	108.9 (d)	118.1 (d)	111.8 (d)	177.9 (s)
C-4a	—	—	—	—	—	105.4 (s)
C-5	120.4 (d)	126.7 (d)	125.5 (d)	125.8 (d)	125.9 (d)	160.8 (s)
C-6	129.4 (d)	127.4 (d)	145.4 (s)	146.2 (s)	145.9 (s)	98.6 (d)
C-7	109.7 (d)	120.4 (d)	130.4 (d)	130.7 (d)	130.7 (d)	166.1 (s)
C-8	154.2 (s)	145.2 (s)	149.9 (s)	150.1 (s)	150.1 (s)	93.2 (d)
C-8a	—	—	—	—	—	161.8 (s)
C-9	113.9 (s)	119.2 (s)	178.5 (s)	178.5 (s)	179.2 (s)	—
C-10	137.6 (s)	135.9 (s)	181.6 (s)	181.2 (s)	181.6 (s)	—
C-11	—	—	120.0 (s)	123.0 (s)	120.3 (s)	—
C-12	—	—	135.6 (s)	135.5 (s)	136.0 (s)	—
C-13	—	—	133.8 (s)	133.8 (s)	134.0 (s)	—
C-14	—	—	123.0 (s)	122.9 (s)	122.6 (s)	—
C-1'	—	—	—	—	95.4 (d)	123.0 (s)
C-2'	—	—	—	—	67.9 (d)	130.6 (d)
C-3'	—	—	—	—	68.9 (d)	116.8 (d)
C-4'	—	—	—	—	70.4 (d)	160.8 (s)
C-5'	—	—	—	—	68.4 (d)	116.8 (d)
C-6'	—	—	—	—	17.2 (q)	130.6 (d)
—COOH _s	205.6 (s)	193.2 (s)	—	—	—	—
—COCH ₃	33.4 (q)	31.7 (q)	—	—	—	—
Ar-CH ₃	21.0 (q)	20.9 (q)	21.2 (q)	21.4 (q)	21.5 (q)	—
—OCOCH ₃	—	169.7 (s), 169.2 (s)	169.0 (s), 168.8 (s)	169.2 (s), 168.8 (s), 167.7 (s)	169.7 (s), 169.4 (s), 169.1 (s)	—
—OOOCH ₃	—	19.0 (q), 20.6 (q)	20.7 (q)	20.8 (q)	20.9 (q), 20.5 (q)	—
ArOCH ₃	—	—	55.7 (q)	—	—	57.3 (q)

^a Spectra run in DMSO-d₆ and δ values downfield from TMS: $\delta_{\text{TMS}} = \delta_{\text{DMSO-d}_6} + 89.6$ ppm.

^b Spectra run in CDCl₃ and δ values downfield from TMS: $\delta_{\text{TMS}} = \delta_{\text{CDCl}_3} + 76.9$ ppm.

procumbens constitutes the second report of the natural occurrence of this compound.

The δ_C values of physcion diacetate (**2b**) compare excellently with those reported¹⁴ earlier, thereby further authenticating its characterisation. The carbon chemical shifts of emodin triacetate (**2d**) and frangulin A pentaacetate (**2g**) were assigned by comparison with the reported δ_C values of the parent anthraquinone¹⁴ and those of **2b** and a number of substituted anthraquinones¹⁴. It may be noted that the carbon chemical shifts of the anthraquinone moiety of **2g** are almost identical with those of the corresponding carbon atoms of **2d**, except for C-2, C-3 and C-4. C-2 and C-4 of **2g** are shifted upfield by 5.5 and 6.3 ppm, respectively, while C-3 of **2g** is deshielded by 5.0 ppm compared to the corresponding carbon atoms of **2d**. These differences in the δ_C values of C-2, C-3 and C-4 of **2g** and **2d** are in excellent accord with the changed additive parameters arising out of the replacement of the acetyl group at C-3 of **2d** by an acetylated sugar moiety in **2g**. The δ_C values of the acetylated sugar part agree¹⁵ well with those expected for triacetyl rhamnoside. The chemical shift of C-1' and that of hydrogen attached to it, settle the stereochemistry of the glycosidic linkage in **2g** to be β .

The assignments of the carbon chemical shifts of kaemferide (**3**) were made by comparison with the reported δ_C values of simple flavone¹⁶ and substituted flavone derivatives¹⁶, particularly with those having hydroxy or methoxy groups at C-3. It has been observed¹⁶ that introduction of a hydroxyl group at C-3 of flavone has not only shifted C-3 downfield by a larger than expected amount 33 ppm, but also

causes downfield shift of C-2' and C-6' by ~2.0-2.3 ppm and an upfield shift of C-4' by ~1.5-2.0 ppm. Moreover, the *ortho* effect of the C-3 hydroxyl group on C-2 is also larger (~15 ppm) than expected. In conformity with these observations, C-3 of **2g** shows a downfield shift of 31.0 ppm, while those of its C-2' and C-6' are shifted downfield by 3.1 ppm. Further, C-2 of **2g** is also shifted upfield by 13.5 ppm and its C-4' shows an upfield shift of ~0.7 ppm compared to the corresponding carbon atoms of 4'-methoxyflavone¹⁶. The presence of another hydroxyl group at C-5 of **3** was also supported by the chemical shift of its C-4 appearing at 177.9 ppm which is very close to the reported¹⁶ value (177 ppm) for 3,5-dihydroxyflavone derivative. C-4 of 3-unsubstituted 5-hydroxyflavone appears at a much more downfield¹⁶ (183 ppm). Thus the ¹³C nmr spectral data of **3** not only confirm its assigned structure, but also corroborate the diagnostic ¹³C nmr spectral features of the flavonoids reported by the previous workers¹⁶.

The isolation from *R. procumbens* of the above seven compounds comprising of four different structural types containing a naphthalene, an anthraquinone, a flavone and a phthalide moiety, represents a unique chemotaxonomical feature.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in a Kofler block and are uncorrected. Uv spectra were measured in 95% aldehyde-free ethanol. Ir spectra were run in KBr disc in a Beckman 20 infrared spectrophotometer. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded in a 80 MHz Varian CFT-20 instrument in CDCl₃ (unless otherwise stated) using TMS as the internal standard. ¹³C nmr spectra were also run in the same instrument at 20 MHz using the same solvent and internal standard. Mass spectra were taken in MS-9 and DS-55 instruments equipped with direct inlet system and operating at 70 eV. *m/z* values of the more intense peaks are given and the figures in the first brackets attached to each *m/z* values indicate relative intensities. Silica gel (60-100 mesh) was used for column chromatography and silica gel G for tlc. Anhydrous Na₂SO₄ was used for drying organic solvents and petrol (petroleum ether) used had b.p. 60-80°.

Isolation of musizin (1a), physcion (2a) and emodin (2c): Air-dried powdered whole plant of *R. procumbens* (6 kg) was exhaustively extracted with petrol in a soxhlet apparatus (1 kg/batch). The total petrol extract on concentration deposited a golden yellow solid which was filtered and chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) eluate gave **1a** (3.0 g), crystallised from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 160°; λ_{max} 226, 262 and 332 nm (log ε 4.32, 4.22 and 3.69); ν_{max} 3260-3380 (OH), 1622 (chelated C=O), 1605, 1580 and 1450 cm⁻¹ (Ar nucleus); *m/z* 216 (*M*⁺, 100), 202(38), 201(99), 199(14), 198(84), 197(20), 169(16), 156(10), 155(70), 145(32), 144(12), 141(18), 139(10), 128(20), 127(90), 126(20), 117(10),

116(22), 115(76), 109(12), 102(12), 101(16), 100(10), 99(14), 91(30) and 89(20). Treatment of **1a** with Ac₂O/Py gave diacetyl musizin (**1b**), crystallised from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 186°; λ_{max} 225 and 286 nm (log ε 4.61 and 3.66); ν_{max} 1250, 1760 (OAc), 1697 (conj. C=O), 1630, 1600, 1565 and 1435 cm⁻¹ (Ar nucleus); δ 7.59 (1H, dd, *J*₁ 9Hz and *J*₂ 3Hz, H-5), 7.50 (1H, fine splitting, H-4), 7.37 (1H, dd, *J*₁ 9Hz and *J*₂ 8.5Hz, H-6), 7.02 (1H, dd, *J*₁ 8.5Hz and *J*₂ 3Hz, H-7), 2.45 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.32 and 2.30 (each 3H, s, ArOCOCH₃) and 2.25 (3H, s, ArCOCH₃); *m/z* 300 (*M*⁺, 16), 258(26), 217(30), 216(99), 215(10), 202(14), 201(100), 200(10), 198(40), 187(10), 155(14), 144(12), 141(10), 128(10), 127(20), 116(16) and 115(40).

The filtrate after separation of **1a** was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) eluate gave **2a** (0.06 g), crystallised from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 202°; λ_{max} 224, 256, 265 and 288 nm (log ε 4.16, 3.90, 3.91 and 3.88); ν_{max} 3100-3400 (OH), 1685 (conj. unchelated C=O), 1635 (chelated C=O), 1585, 1490 and 1465 cm⁻¹ (Ar nucleus); δ 12.18 and 11.98 (each 1H, s, Ar-OH), 7.52 (1H, br. s, H-5), 7.26 (1H, d, *J* 3Hz, H-4), 6.98 (1H, br. s, H-7), 6.59 (1H, d, *J* 3Hz, H-2), 3.87 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃) and 2.35 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃); *m/z* 284 (*M*⁺, 100), 256(11), 255(23), 254(17), 241(21), 227(11), 226(13), 213(11) and 128(17). Acetylation of **2a** with Ac₂O/Py gave diacetyl physcion (**2b**), crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH (9 : 1), m.p. 174°.

Further elution of the above chromatogram with petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) gave **2c** (6.0 g), crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH (9 : 1), m.p. 253°; λ_{max} 216, 255 and 311 nm (log ε 3.80, 3.68 and 3.64); ν_{max} 3340-3540 (OH), 1680 (conj. C=O), 1620 (chelated C=O), 1600, 1565 and 1480 cm⁻¹ (Ar nucleus); *m/z* 270 (*M*⁺, 100), 242(12), 213(10), 180(78), 179(20), 152(12), 151(26) and 95(10). Emodin triacetate (**2d**) prepared by acetylation of emodin with Ac₂O/Py, crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH (9 : 1), m.p. 195°; ν_{max} 1240 and 1770 (phenolic OAc) and 1665 cm⁻¹ (conj. C=O); δ 7.85 (1H, d, *J* 1.5Hz, H-5), 7.82 (1H, d, *J* 2Hz, H-4), 7.15 (1H, d, *J* 2Hz, H-2), 7.10 (1H, d, *J* 1.5Hz, H-7), 2.40 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.34 (6H, s, Ar-OCOCH₃) and 2.25 (3H, s, Ar-OCOCH₃).

Isolation of chrysophanol (2e), frangulin A (2f), 7-hydroxy-5-methoxyphthalide (4), kaemferide (3) and a further quantity of emodin (2c): The marc left after extraction with petrol was then successively extracted with CHCl₃ and MeOH. The concentrated CHCl₃ extract was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) eluate gave **2e** (0.06 g), crystallised from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 192°; λ_{max} 225, 255, 277 and 288 nm (log ε 4.59, 4.36, 4.06 and 4.08); ν_{max} 3640(OH), 1680 (conj. C=O), 1625 (chelated C=O), 1600, 1510 and 1470 cm⁻¹ (Ar nucleus); δ 11.88 and 11.99 (each 1H, s, Ar-OH), 7.46-7.77 (3H, ill-resolved m, H-4, H-5 and H-3), 7.01-7.23 (2H, m, H-2 and H-7) and 2.39 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃); *m/z* 254 (*M*⁺, 100), 253(11), 239(14), 237(17), 226(54), 225(21), 198(32), 197(55), 181(14), 180(14), 169(15), 152(35), 151(20), 150(11), 141(20), 139(11),

127(17) and 115(24). The later fractions of petrol-EtOAc (50:1) eluate gave small amount of physcion. The petrol-EtOAc (10:1) eluate in the above chromatography also gave **2c** (30 g). The petrol-EtOAc (5:1) eluate gave **4** (0.012 g), crystallised from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 176°; λ_{\max} 219, 256, 292 and 320 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.68, 4.43, 3.87 and 3.43); ν_{\max} 3260(OH), 1730 (>C=O), 1610, 1500, 1475 (Ar nucleus) and 870 cm^{-1} (1,2,3,5-tetrasubstituted-Ar nucleus); δ (DMSO- d_6) 6.50 (1H, d, J 3Hz, H-4), 6.41 (1H, d, J 3Hz, H-6), 5.10 (2H, s, H_2 -3) and 3.75 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃); m/z 180 (M^+ , 70), 179(18), 152(10), 151(100), 95(11) and 44(21). Acetate of **4** crystallised from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 139°; δ 6.73 (1H, d, J 3Hz, H-6), 6.63 (1H, d, J 3Hz, H-4), 5.15 (2H, s, H_2 -3), 3.85 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃) and 2.35 (3H, s, Ar-OCOCH₃).

Further elution of the above chromatogram with petrol-EtOAc (1:1) afforded **3** (0.12 g), crystallised from MeOH, m.p. 220°; λ_{\max} 208, 267 and 369 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.41, 4.22 and 4.28); ν_{\max} 3160-3480 (OH), 1665 (conj. C=O), 1610, 1590, 1500 and 1415 cm^{-1} (Ar nucleus); m/z 300 (M^+ , 100), 299(18), 272(4), 271(8), 257(12), 243(3), 229(3), 150(5), 121(18) and 105(2). Acetylation of **3** with Ac₂O/Py gave its triacetyl derivative, crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH (9:1), m.p. 201°; ν_{\max} 1240 and 1770(OAc), 1635 cm^{-1} (conj. C=O); δ 7.85 (2H, d, J 10Hz, H-2' and H-6'), 7.22 (2H, d, J 10Hz, H-3' and H-5'), 6.82 (1H, d, J 3Hz, H-6), 6.62 (1H, d, J 3Hz, H-8), 3.89 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃) and 2.42, 2.32 and 2.30 (each 3H, s, Ar-OCOCH₃).

The above chromatogram was then washed with EtOAc and the eluate on evaporation gave **2f** (0.18 g), crystallised from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 230° (Found: C, 60.30; H, 4.90. C₂₁H₂₀O₉ requires C, 60.57; H, 4.80%); λ_{\max} 225, 264 and 286 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.47, 4.24 and 4.10); ν_{\max} 3340-3380(OH), 1665 (conj. C=O), 1620(chelated C=O), 1600, 1560 and 1475 cm^{-1} (Ar nucleus). Acetylation of **2f** with Ac₂O/Py gave the pentaacetyl derivative **2g**, crystallised from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 184°; ν_{\max} 1250 and 1760(OAc), 1675 cm^{-1} (conj. C=O); δ 7.90 (1H, br.s, H-5), 7.78 (1H, d, J 3Hz, H-4), 7.05 (1H, d, J 3Hz, H-2), 6.99 (1H, d, J 2Hz, H-7), 5.58 (1H, m, H-1'), 5.45 (1H, m, H-5'), 5.35, 5.25 and 5.01 (each 1H, m, H-2', H-3' and H-4'), 2.43 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.37 and 2.32 (each 3H,

s, Ar-OCOCH₃), 2.14, 2.00 and 1.92 (each 3H, s, R-OCOCH₃) and 1.15 (3H, d, J 6Hz, H₃-6').

Methanol extract afforded only traces of **2a**, **2c**, **2e**, **2f**, **3** and **4**.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. B. C. Das, Institut de Chimie des Substances Naturelles, Gif-Sur-Yvette, France, and Dr. G. F. Smith, University of Manchester, U.K., for mass spectra and Prof. S. Ghosal, B.H.U., for the authentic samples. One of the authors (A.C.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. R. H. THOMSON, "Naturally Occurring Quinones", Academic Press, New York, 1972.
2. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1956.
3. O. J. GOVELL, F. E. KING and J. W. W. MORGAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 702.
4. K. TSUKIDA, *J. Pharm. Soc. Jpn.*, 1954, **74**, 398; M. V. BARGENT and D. O'N. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1969, 2763.
5. W. DE LA RUE and H. MÜLLER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1858, 298; D. G. BUCKLEY, E. RITCHIE, W. C. TAYLOR and L. M. YOUNG, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1972, 843.
6. L. HORHAMMER, G. BITTNER and H. P. HORHAMMER, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1964, **51**, 310.
7. T. J. MABRY, K. R. MARKHAM and M. B. THOMAS, "The Systematic Identification of Flavonoids", Academic Press, London, 1970.
8. L. OPITZ and R. HANSEL, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1971, **304**, 228.
9. J. B. STOTHERS, "C-13 NMR Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1972.
10. G. O. LEVY, R. L. LICHTER and G. L. NELSON, "Carbon-13 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., John Wiley, New York, 1980.
11. W. KITCHING, M. BULLPIT and D. GARTSHORE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1977, **42**, 2411.
12. E. WENKERT, H. E. GOTTLIEB, O. R. GOTTLIEB, M. O. FERREIRA DAS and M. D. FORMIGA, *Phytochemistry*, 1976, **15**, 1547.
13. P. L. MAJUMDER, D. BANDOPADHYAY and S. JOARDAR, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. I*, 1982, 1191.
14. G. HÖFLE, *Tetrahedron*, 1977, **33**, 1968.
15. W. VOELTER, V. BITIK and E. BREITMAIER, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1973, **38**, 2054.
16. B. TERNAI and K. R. MARKHAM, *Tetrahedron*, 1976, **32**, 565; E. WENKERT and H. E. GOTTLIEB, *Phytochemistry*, 1977, **16**, 1811; A. PELTER, R. S. WARD and T. I. GRAY, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. I*, 1976, 2476.